
IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND SOCIAL NETWORKING IN ACADEMIC LIBRARY SERVICES

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Abstract:

This paper high lights on different types of social media tools, various aspects of social networking and its application to academic library services. The students and staff are updating their knowledge through social networking .Now a days, Social media tools are important in each and every discipline. Social media helps the library professionals to make things easy for them and for their readers to increase their capacity to build good relationships among library staff and library users.

Keywords: *Social Media, Social Networking, academic libraries.*

Introduction:

Social media creates an effective platform to make people access and share their information with other people with far distance .social media are used by the people to connect themselves with their friends and relatives and groups through the different social media .Similarly, in the field of digital library ,most of the users are using E-learning and social networking sites. To satisfy the users many libraries are providing services through different social media like face books, Twitter and Myspace during the last couple of year,

1. Concept of Social Media:

Social media are computer-mediated tools that allow people to create, share or exchange information, ideas and pictures/videos in virtual communities and networks.

Social media is defined as” a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated

content. Furthermore, social media depends on mobile and web –based technologies to create interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-create, discuss and modify user-generated content.

Social media is web based communication media which a user can interact with other user in terms of social life, professional life, and educational purpose

2. Types of Social Media:

Social media can be categories based on their characteristics. These are as follows,

2.1 Social Networking Sites:

Social networking sites have becomes an integrated part of our daily lives. Social networking sites are profile based websites that allow users to maintain social relationships by viewing, visiting and sharing their lists of social connections with other member

2.2 Blogs :

It is a website that contains online personal reflections, comments, and often

hyperlinks, videos, and photographs provided by the writer. By creating a blog you 'll be able to disseminate information to lots of people at one time,

2.3 Wikis:

It is a webpage which allows anyone to edit, modify text and edit other content. A wiki (sometimes spelled "Wiki") is a server program that allows users to collaborate in forming the content of a Web site. A wiki provides a simplified interface. It is not necessary to know HTML. At any time, contributors can review the history of the page they are working on or preview the Web page before publishing it. Example is Wikipedia.

2.4 Media sharing:

This types of social media are very popular now-a days among the people. some of the examples of media sharing are You Tubes and Flickr. This type of social media tools allow the users specially to upload and share the multimedia files like video, images, songs over the internet ,

2.5 Bookmarking Sites :

Book marking tools allow users to store, tag, organise, share and search for bookmarks (links) to resource online. Users can create personal collection of bookmark and they can share these bookmarks publicly or with member of s particular group. It also identifies other users with similar interest, identifies resources tagged similarly to one's resources.

2.6 Forums:

It is an online discussion platform where a group a situation or meeting in which people can talk about a problem or matter especially of public interest: a forum for debate/discussion.

A *forum* is a public discussion. It can refer to a meeting, a meeting house or any conversation that is available publicly

2.7 Microblogging:

It is web based interface application which a user or subscribe to get update the short form of like text, video link from other user that they have subscribed and can post a short piece of digit such as text, video or image. Twitter is one of the example of microblogging.

Social Networking:

Social networking has become one of the most important parts of our daily life which enables us to communicate with each other. A Social networking is an online service, platform or site that focuses on building and reflecting of social network or social relations among people who share interest and activities. Most social network services are web based and provide means for users to interact over the internet. Social networking facilitates us to also enhance our viewpoints as it enables us certain interactive learning activities.

1. Web Tools available for Social Networking:

- Yahoo Group – <http://group.yahoo.com>
- My space - www.myspace.com
- Town crossing – www.towncrossing.com
- Bebo - www.bebo.com
- Blogtronic - www.blogtronic.com
- Delicious - <http://delicious.com>
- Linked in - <http://linkedin.com>
- Face book - www.facebook.com

2. Use of Social Networking sites in Higher Education :

- Create profile themselves

- Connect with other user sending as “ request” (may be accepted or denied)
- Manage the list of friend and searching related links
- Sending messages
- Posting tagging and sharing object with others and
- Customize a range of aspects, from layout and design to function and selective disclosures of information to different user.

3. Social Networking Sites for Research

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Social networking sites plays a vital role in the field of scholarly communication especially in the field of research. Many of them exclusively designed for researchers in order to save their time and energy which will ultimately help them to organize their research work and increase their productivity in number of ways. In India social networking research tools must be promoted among the research scholars to utilize for their research.

As library professionals, we have to take initiative to introduce these tools/sites to the research community in our concerned institutions, as well as make them available in the library for the better use, This can solve the research communities practical problems in search ,cite, annotate and collaborate for their research.

4. Types of Social networking Sites :

The Social Networking sites can be broadly divided into four :

- Sites for Collaboration and network with professional.
- Sites for Citation management
- Sites for Bookmarking
- Sites for File sharing and Online storage.

Social Networking Tools and its Application in Academic Library Services:

Social networking tools helps academic librarian to share information with Research scholars and students in the easiest way for academic library environment. In the digital era academic librarian can keep constant touch and effective interaction with teaching faculty, Students and research scholars .There are lot of social network tools used in library services

• Facebook

It is one of the popular social sites that are used by people worldwide. Facebook is librarian friendly. In recent days many library has its own facebook account .The college libraries use this social media to provide various types of library information i.e Library announcement, latest addition, best user, new services, due date details. etc.

• YouTube :

This is one of the best social media site widely used by the libraries in and around the world. Library video and e-learning tutorials, events and others video library services can be effectively promote and webcast through YouTube.

• Wikipedia :

Wikipedia is an online encyclopaedia updated by users. This tool helps the library to share the information about the history of library, its holdings, library resources, library services, and also different section of library can connect with the library patrons. So that user could know the collection and other information about library.

• Flickr :

Flickr is another web tool available under web 2.0 technology especially for saving and exchanging photos or pictures. Flickr is created and manage by Yahoo. It

is a social media basically used for sharing of bulk photos with unlimited storage space .Flickr is also useful for preserving maps or geographic information related digital collection which could be exchanged with others. Library can share poster, brochure, photo collection of workshops, conference and different program that are organised with in the campus.

- **Myspace :**

Myspace (<http://www.myspace.com>) is very popular social networking site. It allows the user to create their profile with aim to provide better services by way of making friends, groups, sharing views, resources, images and videos.

- **Twitter :**

Twitter is another social networking site which most people are started using now a days, Twitter enables its users to send and read short messages called tweets. Those who need can register themselves freely and send their tweets, Library can also host its twitter site to remain in contact with its readers to get their live feed back. Website – <http://devitwitter.com>.

- **Library Blog :**

Blog is a discussion and information site published in internet. Being a service organ, the library should also have an account to communicate its users bout the latest developments. The younger generation are mostly spend time on online, and hence the library can have tough with them by having its own blog. The blog has to be updated regularly with the relevant information.

- **Linkedin :**

This social networking site for professionals is a great way to get library patrons connected with the people that can help them to find information. Whether that's you faculty, authors, historians or

other sources they find them in your Linkedin network.

- **Library Websites :**

Today Library websites is very common for the Librarian to represents their resources. Where they are providing the information relating to their services, what they provide, and different events what they organise from time to time. Exhibition like books, different products etc now many libraries have organize their own websites.

Benefits of Social networking in Academic Libraries:

Following are the benefits of application of social networking in Academic libraries.

1. Readers can actively form reader's group in social networking to share experience of library use, which includes topics like library skills, in using various e-resources, success stories of information retrievals etc..
2. Most of the social media are very user friendly and simple and its need no extra training.
3. It helps reader in self learning programme.
4. Social networking research sites can help researcher to communicate with other researchers and stakeholders easily.
5. Library can promote library resources using social media for Orientation programme of the e books, e Journals.etc.
6. Library can easily share , connect with other libraries and members free of cost
7. Most of the social media are freely available on internet.
8. It increase the uses of library services & resources interaction with library patrons
9. It improve innovation and learning.

10. Reduces travel cost and time.

Limitations:

Following are the limitations of social media

1. Lack of knowledge how to use social media.
2. Too many social media tools to learn
3. Low interest of Librarians in learning and utilizing social media.
4. Slow speed of internet
5. Lack of privacy and identity theft.
6. Need interrupted internet connectivity and electricity connection.
7. Lack of validity of information.
8. Inadequate training opportunities for library staff.

Conclusion:

The social networking websites has become very essential in the day to day life. Social networks play key role to connect the people frequently in varies types of fields. Social media tools are important in each and every discipline now a days. Similarly ,Library professionals are using these tools for purpose of the promoting library services and resources.In the Digital library section library professionals are connecting another library professionals all over the world to exchange their latest development in the field of library and information science. In the digital library environment, the library professionals required more social network awareness.

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